

Biographies of Eminent Monks

Volume II

(DRAFT!!!! – DO NOT CITE!!)

Imre Galambos

1. Kumārajīva

Kumārajīva (Jiumoluoshi 鳩摩羅什) means Age of a Child (*tongshou* 童壽). He was a native of India, and his family for generations served as chief ministers. Kumārajīva's grandfather Daduo 達多 (Datta?) was an extraordinary person whose name was well known in their country. His father Jiumoyan 鳩摩炎 (Kumārayāna?) was intelligent and had exceptional integrity, and was about to inherit the post of chief minister but instead declined it and became a monk. He went east, crossing the Pamirs.¹ Having heard of his abandoning worldly glory, the king of Kucha (Qiuci 龜茲) held him in high esteem. He came in person to the edge of the city to welcome him and to request him to become a state preceptor. The king had a younger sister who had just turned nineteen. Knowledgeable and bright, she could learn anything she read through once, and she could recite by heart anything just by hearing it. She had on her body a red birthmark which foretold that she would give birth to a sage son. Rulers of different countries had requested to marry her but she would not consent to this. But when she saw Kumārayāna, she wished to marry him, and thus [the king] compelled him to marry her.

Soon she conceived Kumārajīva. When he was still in his mother's womb, she sensed that her intuition and capacity for supernatural understanding was twice as strong as what it was normally. She had often heard of the virtue of the great monastery of Queli 雀梨, and that it had monks who had attained the Way. Consequently, together with noble women from the royal family and virtuous nuns, she all day long engaged in laying out offerings, pure fasting and listening to the teaching. Kumārajīva's mother suddenly spontaneously understood the language of India 天竺語, and could grasp the profound sense of even the most difficult words, so that everyone in the congregation marvelled at it. A certain arhat called Dharmaghoṣa (Damoqusha 達摩瞿沙) said: "This must be because she conceived a sage son. To speak of it, this is the sign of Śāriputra in the tomb." After Kumārajīva was born, she forgot again the language she had learned earlier. In a short while, she desired to become a nun but her husband did not consent to this. Later on, she gave birth to another son whom they named Puṣyadeva (Fushatipo 弗沙提婆). At one time she went out of the city for a trip and saw at the graveyard some dry bones lying around in disarray, which made her to contemplate on the roots of suffering, and so she vowed to become a nun and that she would not eat and drink until her head was shaved. For six days and nights her strength continuously diminished and it was uncertain whether she would survive until sunrise. At that point her husband, out of fear for her, Kumārayāna gave his consent. Since she still would not eat 嘗進 before her head was shaven, he gave orders to cut off her hair and only then did she eat and drink. The next morning she accepted the precepts and began enjoying the methods of meditation. She fully devoted herself to them and studied without tirelessly until she obtained the first results.

¹ Where do you have to come from for you to be coming eastward when you cross the Pamirs?

At the age of seven, Kumārajīva followed her and became a monk. He received scriptures from his master and chanted a thousand gathas a day. As each gatha had thirty-two syllables, this came to thirty-two thousand syllables. Once he excelled in chanting the abhidharma, the teacher explained to him their meaning, which was quick to grasp (lit. understood himself) down to the most obscure parts. At that time, because the people of Kucha gave lots of offerings to the his mother, the younger sister of the king, she took Kumārajīva with her and fled from her.

Kumārajīva was nine years old, he followed his mother across the Indus River 辛頭河 to Kashmir 罽賓. There they met a famous and virtuous master called Bandhudatta 槃頭達多, who was the cousin of the king of Kashmir. He was perceptive and wholesome to the extreme, and stood out among his contemporaries with his intelligence and broad knowledge. He was well versed in the nine sections of the Tripitaka; he would write a thousand gathas from dawn until noon and then chant a thousand gathas from noon until evening. His fame spread to many countries and people came from far and near to study under him. When Kumārajīva arrived, he greeted Badhudatta with the rites of a master. He received from him the *Kṣudraka-piṭaka* 雜藏, the *Madhyama Āgama* 中舍 and *Dīrgha Āgama* 長舍, amounting to four million words in total.

Bandhudatta often commended Kumārajīva for his brilliance and with time his reputation came to the knowledge of the king. The king immediately asked him to come to the palace and assembled experts of other teachings to jointly overcome him in debate. As the debate began, the experts of other teachings underestimated him on account of his young age and thought that he was impertinent. Kumārajīva seized the opportunity and defeated them so that the experts admitted their defeat and, ashamed, could not utter a word. As a result, the king had even greater admiration for him, offering him a daily provision of a pair of cured geese, three *dou* of polished round grain rice, three *dou* of wheat flour and six *sheng* of cheese. This was the highest amount of provision given to a foreigner. The monks of the monastery where he stayed assigned five ordained monks and ten śrāmaṇeras to tend to him and to do cleaning. He was kept in such high respect.

At the age of twelve, his mother took him and returned to Kucha. [Along the way,] the various kingdoms all offered him high titles but he remained indifferent to these. When Kumārajīva's mother arrived with him at the Northern Mountains of the Yuezhi, an arhat saw them and marvelled at him. He said to his mother: “You must always protect him! If this śrāmaṇera does not does violate the precepts until the age of thirty-five, he will greatly promote the Buddha's dharma and save countless people, just like Upagupta. If he cannot fully observe the precepts, he will not be able to do all this but will merely be an intelligent person who can accompany a dharma master.”

Kumārajīva proceeded farther and arrived in the kingdom of Kashgar 沙勒國, carrying on his head his begging bowl and repeating to himself: “The bowl is very large, how come it is so light?” In an instant, it became unbearably heavy so that he lost his voice and put it down. When his mother asked why, he said: “It is just that because your son's mind has division/separation 分別, the bowl is now light, now heavy.”

After this, they stopped in Kashgar for a year. In the winter, he chanted the *Abhidharma*, completely absorbing the chapters “Ten Gates” 十門 and “Cultivation of Wisdom” 修智, and

fully understanding their nuances. He also had no difficulties with the Six Pāda 六足. In Kashgar, there lived a śramaṇa by the name of Xijian 喜見 (Joyful to See), who told the king: “This śramaṇera should not be underestimated! Your Majesty should ask him to begin expounding the doctrine. This would have two benefits. The first is that that the śramaṇas of our kingdom would become ashamed of their inadequacy and would necessarily be compelled to make more effort. The second is that the king of Kucha would certainly think that since Kumārajīva is a native of his country, whoever shows respect to Kumārajīva is showing respect to him, and for that reason he is bound to establish good relations with us.” The king approved the plan. A large congress was set up and Kumārajīva was asked to take the high seat and expound the *Dharmacakra-pravartana sūtra* 轉法輪經. As expected, the king of Kucha sent a formal embassy to repay the gesture of friendliness.

In his spare time when he was not expounding the teaching, Kumārajīva sought out the scriptures of other teachings. He excelled in studying the *Weituohanduo lun* 圍陀含多論 and absorbed the arts of literary composition and debating. In addition, he read through the four Vedas and the theories of the five fields of knowledge 五明. He fully acquired the art of divining through Yin and Yang and astrology, was able to anticipate good and bad fortune, with predictions of great precision. In terms of his nature, he was open-minded and did not engage in trivial matters. The practitioners all viewed him with suspicion but Kumārajīva remained content in his heart and did not care about them.

At that time there were two brothers, one was the heir of the king of Yarkend 莎車, the other the supreme commander of the army. They gave up their kingdom and decided to become śramaṇas. The elder brother’s name was Suryabhadra 須利耶跋陀, the younger’s Suryasoma 須耶利蘇摩.² Suriyasoma had unsurpassed talents and skills, he devoted himself to teaching the Mahāyāna. His elder brother and other learned men all considered him their teacher. Kumārajīva also admired and treated him with respect. Their friendship became stronger and stronger. Later on, Suryasoma expounded the *Anavatapta sūtra* 阿耨達經 for Kumārajīva. Hearing that the fields of human world are all empty without physical manifestation, Kumārajīva asked in amazement: “What is the point of this sutra if it destroys all dharmas?” Suryasoma replied: “The many dharmas seen by the eye do not really exist.” Kumārajīva used to rely on his visual faculties but now he scrutinized the big and the small over and over. Only then did he understand that the principle has a source. Then he focussed his efforts on studying the *Vaipulya sutra* 方等. He sighed, saying: “Formerly, I have studied the Hīnayāna, like a man who does not know gold and thinks that brass is the most wonderful metal!” Thereupon he strived to attain the essence [of the scriptures], received and recited the *Madhyamaka* and *Śata śāstras* 中百二論, as well as the *Dvādaśamukhaśāstra* 十二門.

In a little while, Kumārajīva followed his mother to travel to the kingdom of Wensu 溫宿 (Aksu?), located to the north of Kucha. At the time, there was a monk 道士 in Wensu who was a highly skilled debater, famous for his talent in many countries. He hit with his hand the king’s drum and made a vow: “If someone defeats me in debate, I will cut off my head for him.”

² Technically the first half of the names of the brothers is different (須利耶跋陀 and 須耶利蘇摩) but a syllable is probably omitted from the second name.

Kumārajīva came to him and asked him to compare the two teachings (i.e. Hīnayāna and Mahāyāna). The debater was confused and at a loss, he prostrated himself and took refuge [in the teaching of the Buddha].

Thus Kumārajīva's fame spread east of the Pamir and his reputation reached the Yellow River region. The king of Kucha personally came to see him in Wensu to bring him back to his own kingdom. Kumārajīva widely expounded the sutras, people in the four directions admired him and there was nobody who could contend with him. The king's daughter was a nun called Akṣayamati. She had widely read the sutras and had an especially profound understanding of the essence of meditation (*dhyāna*). People said that she had already attained the second realization. When she heard [Kumārajīva's expounding of] the teaching, she leapt up in joy. Thereupon she set up a great congress and asked him to expound the mysteries of Vaipulya scriptures. Kumārajīva explicated the concept that all dharmas are empty and possess no self, and made a clear analysis of the idea that the five *skandhas* and eighteen *dhātus* are merely empty names without reality. Everyone in the audience was moved by sadness and regret, resenting the fact that realization came to them so late. When Kumārajīva was twenty years old, he accepted the precepts in the royal palace. From Vimalaksi he learned the *Shisonglü* 十誦律.

Shortly after this, Kumārajīva's mother said goodbye as she was about to leave for India. She said to Bo Chun 白純, the king of Kucha: "Your kingdom will soon go into decline so I am leaving it." She went to India and there she attained her third realization. Before she left, his mother said to Kumārajīva: "The profound teaching of the Vaipulya should be explicated all over China 真丹. You are the only one who has the ability to spread it eastward but it would be of no benefit to yourself. What shall we do?" Kumārajīva replied: "The Way of the bodhisattva is to benefit others and disregard one's self. If I must make the great teaching spread and can enlighten those living in delusion, I would no regret even if my body would have to suffer the pain of a boiling cauldron." Therefore he remained in Kucha, staying at the Xinsi monastery 新寺.

Later on, in the old palace next to the monastery, he found, for the first time, the *Sutra on the Emission of Light* 放光經. He opened it up and began reading. Māra came over and covered the text so that the wooden plates seemed empty. But Kumārajīva was aware what Māra was doing and vowed to remain persistent. When Māra left, the words appeared and he continued to study and recite the sutra. Then he heard a voice out of nowhere: "You are a wise man, what's the point to read this?" Kumārajīva said: "Trifling demon, leave at once! My mind is firm like the Earth, it cannot be moved."

He stayed [in the monastery] for two years, widely reciting the Mahāyāna sutras and śāstras, mastering their hidden mysteries. The king of Kucha had a golden lion throne made for him, covering it with brocade cushion from the Great Qin 大秦 (Byzantium). He asked Kumārajīva to ascend it and expound the dharma. Kumārajīva said: "My master has still not attained the realization of Mahāyāna teaching, I would like to go and explain to him the teaching personally. I cannot remain here!" Soon after this, coming from a far distance, the great master Bandhudatta arrived. The king said: "Oh, Great Master, what made you come from such a distance?" Bandhudatta replied: "First, I heard about the unusual realization of my disciple; second, I heard that Your Majesty is a great supporter of the Way of the Buddha. This is why, taking no heed to

the difficulties and dangers along the road, I travelled from afar to your marvellous county.” Following his master’s arrival, Kumārajīva happily proceeded to carry out his original idea and expounded to him the *Sutra of the Questions of the Virtuous Woman* 德女問經. He elucidated much concerning the causes and conditions, the empty and nominal. He expounded these first because they were what neither him nor his master believed in before. The master said to Kumārajīva: “What is the amazing thing you see in Mahāyāna that makes you want to revere it?” Kumārajīva replied: “Mahāyāna is profound and pure, it makes it clear that all existent dharmas are empty. Hīnayāna is partial and has many omissions and errors.” The master said: “Your claim that everything is empty is frightening. How could one abandon existent dharmas in favour of emptiness? This is like the case of a fool who asked a master spinner to spin a yarn that was extremely fine. The spinner applied himself to make a yarn as thin as fine dust but the fool complained about it being too thick. The spinner at this flew into a rage and pointed at the air, saying: ‘Here is the fine yarn.’ The fool asked: ‘Why can’t we see it?’ The spinner replied: ‘This yarn is fine to the utmost, I created it with such skill that even I cannot see it, let alone others!’ The fool was very happy and gave the yarn to the weaver who also went along with the pretence. Everyone received a high reward yet in reality the object did not exist. Your empty dharmas are also like this.” Kumārajīva thereupon cited a series of analogies to explain his point. Untiringly going over and over the cases, it took more than a month to be able to convince the master, who then sighed: “When his master cannot understand it, he (i.e. the disciple) succeeds through his will. Our case is a proof to this saying.” With this, he saluted Kumārajīva as his master, saying: “The master is my Mahāyāna teacher, but I am his Hīnayāna teacher!”

Everyone throughout the Western Regions acknowledged Kumārajīva’s brilliance. Every year he gave lectures and the kings all knelt beside his seat, letting him step on them in order to ascend the platform. This is how revered he was. Kumārajīva’s teachings spread throughout the Western Regions and his name was also known in the Eastern Kingdom. At that time Fu Jian 苻堅 usurped the throne in the Guanzhong 關中 region. The king of [Jushi] Qianbu [車師]前部 and the younger brother of the king of Kucha came together to pay respects to Fu Jian. Fu Jian received the two kings at an audience and they said to him: “The Western Regions produce numerous treasures. Send your troops to pacify these lands and request that they submit to you.” In the first month of the thirteenth year of the Jianyuan 建元 reign of Fu Jian (377), a *dingchou* year, the great astrologer submitted a memorial: “There is a star visible on the foreign part of heavens, which means that there will be a man of great virtue and wisdom coming here to help the Middle Kingdom.” Fu Jian said: “I have heard that in the Western Regions there is Kumārajīva, and in Xiangyang 襄陽 there is the śramaṇa Shi Dao’an 釋道安. Could it be that this refers to them?” With that, he sent envoys in search of them. In the second month of the seventeenth year (381), the king of Shanshan 善善, the king of [Jushi] Qianbu and others were once again urging Fu Jian to send his troops on a westward expedition. In the ninth month of the eighteenth year (382), Fu Jian sent Valiant Cavalry General Lü Guang 呂光 and General of Conquering the Lingjiang 陵江 Region Jiang Fei 姜飛 to lead the king of [Jushi] Qianbu, the king of Jushi and others with a force of seventy thousand on an expedition against the kingdoms of Kucha and Wuqi 烏耆 (Yanqi 焉耆, i.e. Karashahr). On the eve of the beginning of the campaign, Fu Jian hosted Lü Guang for a farewell banquet at the Jianzhang Palace 建章宮. He said to Lü Guang: “Now the kings and emperors rule according to the will of heaven but the basis for this is that they love their people like their son. So how could I, coveting their land,

attack them? I do this precisely for the sake of [acquiring] someone who had attained the Way. I have heard that in the Western kingdoms lives Kumārajīva, who has a profound understanding of the attributes of the dharma 法相, is well trained in the art of Yin and Yang and is venerated by younger followers. I have been hoping to procure him very much, as a sage is the greatest treasure of a state. If you conquer Kucha, send Kumārajīva to me by mounted couriers!”

Before the arrival of Lü Guang, Kumārajīva told Bai Chun, the king of Kucha: “The fate of the country is in decline! Very soon there will be strong enemies coming from the east. You should receive them courteously and not resist their attack.” Bai Chun did not heed his advice and fought the invaders. Lü Guang thereupon crushed Kucha and killed Bai Chun, erecting his younger brother Bai Zhen 白震 as the ruler. Even though Lü Guang captured Kumārajīva, he did not appreciate the magnitude of his wisdom. Seeing that he was still young and mocked him as if he was an ordinary person. He forced him to marry the daughter of the king of Kucha but Kumārajīva refused to do this, arguing against it as hard as he could. Lü Guang said: “You should not surpass your late father in behaviour. How dare you resist so stubbornly?” Thereupon they made him drink strong wine and locked them together in a bedroom. Under such coercion Kumārajīva consequently lost his chastity. At other occasions, he was ordered to ride an ox or a wayward horse so that he would fall down. Kumārajīva continually endured the humiliation and showed no sign of being affected by it. Lü Guang felt ashamed and stopped his mockery.

As he was leaving, on the way back Lü Guang camped with his troops at the foot of a mountain. The general and his soldiers were already at rest but Kumārajīva said: “You cannot be here, as this would inevitably bring disaster on yourself. You should move your troops to a higher ground.” But Lü Guang did not listen to him. Sure enough, during the night heavy rain came down, resulting in a violent flood. The water was several *zhang* deep and the dead numbered several thousand. For the first time, Lü Guang secretly felt astonished. Kumārajīva said to him: “This is the land of disaster and death, you should not remain here. My divination shows that you must return quickly. On the road there will be an auspicious place where you can stay.” Lü Guang listened to him and went to Liangzhou 涼州 where he heard the news that Fu Jian had already been slain by Yao Chang 姚萇. Lü Guang’s entire army put on white mourning dress and as a whole approached the area south of the city, where he furtively set himself as the ruler of the region beyond the Pass (i.e. Guanzhong), proclaiming the Tai’an 太安 [Great Peace] reign.

In the first month of the first year of the Tai’an reign (387), there was a great wind in Guzang 姑臧. Kumārajīva said: “This is an inauspicious wind -- there will be treachery and rebellion. But do not worry about it, everything will settle by itself.” Shortly after this, one after the other, Liang Jian 梁謙 and Peng Huang 彭晃 raised a rebellion. But soon they both perished.

In the second year of the Longfei 龍飛 reign of Lü Guang, Juqu Nancheng 沮渠男成, a barbarian from Linsonglushui 臨松盧水, Zhangye 張掖, and his cousin Meng Sun 蒙遜 rebelled. They put Duan Ye 段業, the prefect of Jiankang 建康 on the throne. Lü Guang sent his non-first born son Lü Zuan 呂纂, prefect of Qinzhou 秦州 and Prince of Taiyuan 太, to lead an army of fifty thousand to eradicate them. At the time people said that Duan Ye and the others were a motley crowd, whereas Lü Zuan had the voice of authority and would definitely defeat them. Lü Guang asked Kumārajīva about it, who said: “I have examined this course of action but

have not been able to see its benefit.” Soon Lü Zuan suffered utter defeat in Heli 合梨. Then suddenly Guo Nun 郭麐 raised a revolt. Lü Zuan left his main army and returned with a smaller contingent but was once again defeated by Guo Xin and could barely escape himself.

The Secretariat Supervisor of Lü Guang was Zhang Zi 張資, a kind man with literary talent 文翰 濫雅, whom Lü Guang valued highly. When Zhang Zi became ill, Lü Guang searched for a remedy everywhere. There was a foreign practitioner by the name of Lākṣa (Rākṣa?) who said that he could heal Zhang Zi’s illness. Lü Guang was pleased and rewarded him richly. Kumārajīva knew that Lākṣa was a fraud and so he said to Zhang Zi: “Lākṣa cannot help, he just uselessly increases vexation and expenses. Although the mysteries of destiny are obscure, it is possible to have them assessed.” Accordingly, he made a rope out of five colour threads and tied it into a knot. Then he burned it into ash and threw it in water. [He said:] “If the ashes comes out of the water and turns into a rope, then the illness cannot be cured.” After a short while the ashes floated to the surface and took the shape of a rope. After this, all attempts at healing were ineffective and in a few days, Zhang Zi died.

Soon after this, Lü Guang also died and the throne went to his son Lü Shao 呂紹. Several days later Lü Guang’s side son Lü Zuan killed Lü Shao and erected himself as the ruler, calling his reign Xianning 咸寧. In the second year of the Xianning reign (400), a pig gave birth to a piglet with one body and three heads, and a dragon emerged from a well in the western wing, flew to the palace and coiled up in front of it. It disappeared the next morning. Lü Zuan thought that these were auspicious portents and named the palace the Palace of the Soaring Dragon. Not long after this, there was a black dragon ascending from the Nine Palaces Gates at Dangyang 當陽九宮, so that Lü Zuan renamed the Nine Palaces Gates to Rise of Dragon Gates. Kumārajīva submitted a memorial saying: “These are hidden dragons coming out to roam and a demonic piglet manifesting its aberration. Dragons are creatures of the world of shadows and their appearance and disappearance is tied to specific occasions. In this case their repeated manifestation means that there will be a disaster. Surely, there are some people below scheming to effect changes above. You should keqi 剋綦 and cultivate virtue in order to agree with Heaven’s admonitions.” Lü Zuan did not listen. He played a board game with Kumārajīva and, killing one of his pieces, said: “I cut off the barbarian slave’s head!” Kumārajīva said: “You cannot cut off the barbarian slave’s head, as he is about to cut off someone’s head!” These words contained a hint but Lü Zuan never realized this. Lü Guang’s younger brother had a son called Lü Chao 呂超, whose nickname was Hunu 胡奴 [barbarian slave]. Sure enough, later on Lü Chao killed Lü Zuan and cut off his head, putting his elder brother Lü Long 呂隆 on the throne. People at the time only then realized what Kumārajīva’s words meant.

Kumārajīva stayed in Liangzhou for a number of years but neither Lü Guang nor his sons gave their support to propagating the Way. Therefore, even though he accumulated a profound understanding, he had no nobody to teach it to. Fu Jian had already died and the two of them never had a chance to meet. Yao Chang, who had usurped the throne in Guanzhong, also heard of his high reputation and respectfully sent an invitation to him. The Lü clan, however, thought that Kumārajīva had great tactical resourcefulness and extended powers of understanding, and fearing that he would help Yao Chang in his scheming, did not allow him to go east.

When Yao Chang died, his son Yao Xing 姚興 succeeded him on the throne. He also sent someone with a cordial invitation. In the third month of the third year of the Hongshi 弘始 (401) reign of Yao Xing, trees with joined crowns began to grow in the palace courtyard and the onions in the Xiaoyao Garden 逍遙園 transformed into sweetgrass. It was interpreted as a lucky portent foretelling that a sage would arrive. In the fifth month, Yao Xing sent the Duke of Longxi 隴西公 Yao Shide (Shuode?) 姚碩德 westward on a military campaign against Lü Long. Lü Long's army suffered a great defeat and in the ninth month he submitted a request to capitulate. Only then could Kumārajīva be invited to go to Guanzhong. Thus on the twentieth day of the twelfth month of the same year he arrived in Chang'an, where Yao Xing greeted him with the rites of State Preceptor and showered him with favours. When they met to talk, they would stay there for the whole day, in their exhaustive scrutiny of subtle details, they could tirelessly for an entire year.

Ever since the great teaching spread to the East, beginning with the reign of Emperor Ming 明 (r. 58-75 AD) of the Han and throughout the Wei (220-265) and Jin (265-420) dynasties, there was an increasing number of sutras and śāstras. Yet the translations (publications?) of Yuezhi and Indian translators were often awkward in style and incoherent in meaning. Yao Xing from a young age revered the Three Jewels and was determined to have it propagated for the wider public. Thus when Kumārajīva arrived, he invited him to the Ximing Pavilion 西明閣 and the Xiaoyao Garden 逍遙園 to translate sutras. Kumārajīva recited most of them from memory and had exhaustively explicated all of them. When he translated the text into Chinese, his oral translation was smooth and skilful. Reading the old sutras, he could see that they have many errors in meaning, which were all because earlier foreign translators misinterpreted the meaning so that the text did not correspond to the *fan* version. For this reason Yao Xing made śramaṇas Senglüe 僧碧, Sengqian 僧遷, Faqin 法欽, Daoliu 道流, Daoheng 道恒, Daobiao 道標, Sengrui 僧叟, Sengzhao 僧肇 and others, totalling over eight hundred people, to receive Kumārajīva's instructions concerning the texts' meaning and ordered them to produce a translation of the *Dapin* 大品 (*Dapin Bore jing* 大品般若經). Kumārajīva held the *fan* version and Yao Xing held the old translation of the sutra and used it to compare the two versions and make corrections. Whenever the new translation differed from the old one, the meaning was always perfectly accurate. All around acknowledged his skills and there was no one who did not praise him.

Yao Xing thought that the teachings of the Buddha were truly profound and that he only performed good actions. He believed that the good ford that allows one to leave suffering behind is the great model for ruling the world. Accordingly, he devoted himself to nine part canon and let his mind wander in the twelve divisions. In order to demonstrate the principle of cause and effect, he compiled the *Tong sanshi lun* 通三世論 [Treatise on the Interconnectedness of the Three Ages], the style of which was praised by princes, dukes and others of lower rank. General-in-chief Yao Xian 姚顯, who was Duke of Changshan 常山公, and Left Army General Yao Song 姚嵩, who was Marquis of Ancheng 安城侯, both earnestly believed in dependent arising and karma 緣業 and repeatedly invited Kumārajīva to the Dasi monastery 大寺 in Chang'an to expound his newly translated sutras. He successively translated the *Xiaopin* 小品, *Jingang bore* 金剛波若, *Shizhu* 十住, *Fahua* 法華, *Weimo* 維摩, *Siyi* 思益, *Shoulengyan* 首楞嚴, *Chishi* 持世, *Fozang* 佛藏, *Pusa zang* 菩薩藏, *Yijiao* 遺教, *Puti wuxing* 菩提無行, *Heyu* 呵欲, *Zizai*

wang 自在王, *Yinyuan guan* 因緣觀, *Xiao wuliang shou* 小無量壽, *Xin xianjie* 新賢劫, *Chanjing* 禪經, *Chanfa yao* 禪法要, *Chanyao jie* 禪要解, *Mile chengfo* 彌勒成佛, *Mile xiasheng* 彌勒下生, *Shisonglü* 十誦律, *Shisong jieben* 十誦戒本, *Pusa jieben* 菩薩戒本, *Shilun* 釋論, *Chengshi* 成實, *Shizhu* 十住, *Zhong* 中, *Bai* 百 and *Shi'er men lun* 十二門論. The translations amounted to over three hundred *juan* and they could reveal the divine source and uncover the most subtle meanings. At the time, learned men of the four directions flocked to him from the distance of ten thousand *li*. His towering achievement lasted for ages and even today everyone admires it.

Shi Daosheng 釋道生 of the Longguang 龍光 Monastery had a shrewd understanding of subtle details and a mysterious ability to grasp meanings not in the text 玄構文外; whenever he was concerned that would go wrong in his wording, he came the Guanzhong region and ask Kumārajīva to settle the issue for him. Shi Huiyuan 釋慧遠 from Mount Lu 廬山 had read through the sutras and was instrumental in transmitting the doctrine; but since he was far removed from the Holy One in both time and space, there were many doubtful points he could not decide on, thus he wrote to Kumārajīva to inquire about these. This is described in Huiyuan's biography.

In the beginning, śramaṇa Sengrui, a learned and brilliant man, always followed Kumārajīva and helped with writing down the translations. Kumārajīva often discussed with him the literary style of the West and reflected on how it differed [from that of China], saying: “According to the custom of India, literary compositions are valued very highly, their cadence and rhymes are most valued when they can be accompanied on string instruments. As a general principle, when having an audience with a king, one must praise his virtue. According to the etiquette, when meeting the Buddha, the best way to address him is praising him in verse. The gathas and hymns in the sutras are all in such form. But when we translate the *fan* text into Chinese, we lose its stylistic elegance and sophistication. Even though we may obtain the overall meaning, we distance ourselves from the original literary form. It is similar to giving someone rice that has already been chewed by another person; it has not only lost its taste but makes one vomit.”

Once Kumārajīva composed a verse and presented it to śramaṇa Fahe 法和. The verse said:

The peaks of your mind rear luminous virtue,
Its fragrance flows for ten thousand yojanas;
A sad phoenix on a lonely *wutong* tree,
Its clear voice reaches up to nine-fold heaven.

In total, he composed ten gathas and its literary expressions and metaphors were all like this.

Kumārajīva was fond of Mahāyāna and was determined to propagate it widely. He often sighed, saying: “If I wrote the Abhidharma of Mahāyāna, I would not be comparable to Kātyāyanīputra. Presently, there are very few people with profound knowledge in China. What is there to say if one's wings are broken?” Then with a sorrowful expression he would stop the enterprise. Merely for the sake of Yao Xing, he composed the *Shixiang lun* 實相論 in two *juan* and a commentary to the *Vimalakīrti nirdeśa sūtra*. His words were formed in a literary language and there was

nothing to change in them. The expressions and metaphors were graceful yet restrained, and each of them contained a profound meaning.

As a person, Kumārajīva had a bright and cheerful expression, but stood out among others with his self-confidence. In terms of mental agility and power of comprehension, there were very few who could match him. By nature, he was sincere, kind and magnanimous, and had in his heart an all-encompassing love towards others. He guided others with humility and could do this all day tirelessly.

Once Yao Xing said to Kumārajīva: “Oh, Great Teacher, there is no one in the world who could match your intelligence and extraordinary perceptiveness. If once you leave the world, how can you make sure that your dharma lineage does not discontinue?” Thus he forced Kumārajīva to accept ten singing girls. From this time on, he did not go to his monastery quarters but the emperor had an official residence built specifically for him, which included generous provisions. Every time he went out to preach, he would always first comment about his own words that they were like lotus flowers that grew amidst foul-smelling mud and that people should only pick the lotus flower but not the foetid mud.

Initially, Kumārajīva received the precepts in Kucha from his Vinaya master Vimalaksa. Later, Vimalaksa came to Guanzhong. Hearing that his master arrived, Kumārajīva was overjoyed and greeted him with full rites as his master. Vimalaksa was not aware of him having been forced and thus asked Kumārajīva: “You had a great destiny 大有重緣 in China but how many disciples have received the dharma from you?” Kumārajīva replied: “The sutras and vinaya have not been available in China before. The new sutras and the many śāstras have mostly been translated by myself. I have three thousand followers who have received the teaching from me. Yet because the obstacles generated by my karma were overwhelming, I am unable to live up to your instructions.”³

Furthermore, bhikṣu Beidu 杯渡, who lived in Pengcheng 彭城, upon hearing that Kumārajīva was in Chang’an, sighed and said: “It has been over three hundred years since I jokingly parted with this master but there is no chance of seeing him. I look forward to meet him in a future life.

Before his death, Kumārajīva felt that the four great elements inside him were not well. Thereupon he uttered a divine spell three times and asked his foreign disciples to recite it in order to help him. But before this had an effect, he felt that his conditioned changed to critical. Therefore, he gathered his strength to support his sick body and said goodbye to the multitude of monks with these words: “We met because of the dharma but I really have not exhausted your kindness. Now that I am once again leaving the world, what can I say to express my sadness? Because I am uncultured, I have mistakenly taken on the role of translator, in total translating over three hundred *juan* of sutras and śāstras. The *Shisong* 十誦 is the only text that I have not had a chance to streamline yet. [Yet even in its current form] it preserves the original meaning, there are certainly no mistakes in it. I wish that what I have translated would be transmitted to posterity and would achieve wide circulation. Now in front of you all, I make a solemn vow:

³ In most other versions of the text we have the word “respect” in place of “instructions”, which from the point of view of the meaning of the sentence is a better reading.

should my translations have no errors, after the cremation of my body my tongue will remain unburnt.”

He died in Chang’an, on the twenty-eighth day of the eighth month of the eleventh year of the Hongshi reign (409) of the illegitimate (i.e. Later) Qin dynasty. This year corresponded to the fifth year of the Yixi reign of the Jin 晉 dynasty. His body was cremated in the Xiaoyao Garden according to foreign rites. When the firewood burned down, all of his body, except for the tongue, was reduced to ashes. Later on, a foreign śramaṇa came and claimed that Kumārajīva did not write down one tenth of what he knew.

Initially, Kumārajīva was also called Jiumoluoqipo 鳩摩羅耆婆 (Kumārajīva), as foreigners in most cases receive names based on the names of their parents. Kumārajīva’s father was Kumārayāna(?) and his mother was called Jīva, and this is why his name was the combination of the two.

However, different accounts disagree concerning the month and year of Kumārajīva’s death. Some state that he died in the seventh year of Hongshi (405), others that in the eighth year (406), yet others that in the eleventh year (409). Often the characters writing the numbers ‘seven’ 七 and ‘eleven’ 十一 are mistaken for each other. At the same time, his biography in the list of sutras translated by him says that the year was the first year of the reign (398), although unfortunately it seems that this claim, just like those in the other three sources, cannot be verified.

2. Puṇyatara (Foruoduoluo 弗若多羅)

Puṇyatara means Flower of Merit. He was a native of Kashmir. He became a monk while still young and was praised for his steadfastness in observing the discipline. He was thoroughly familiar with the entire Tripitaka but had especially refined knowledge regarding the *Shisonglü* 十誦律 [Daśa-bhāṇavāra-vinaya] part. He was revered as a master by foreigners. People at the time all said that he had already ascended to sagehood.

He came with his walking staff to the Guanzhong region during the Hongshi reign (399-416) of the illegitimate [i.e. Later] Qin dynasty. Yao Xing, the Qin ruler, treated him as a highly distinguished guest. Kumārajīva also admired his steadfastness in observing the discipline and showed a great deal of respect for him. Initially, even though the dharma of the sutras was being transmitted, there were no explanations of the Vinaya-piṭaka. Learning that Puṇyatara excelled in this section, everyone was in awe of him. On the seventeenth day of the tenth month of the sixth year of the Hongshi reign of the illegitimate [i.e. Later] Qin dynasty, they gathered several hundred doctrinal scholars in the Zhongsi 中寺 monastery in Chang’an, and asked Puṇyatara to recite the *fan* version of the *Shisong*, while Kumārajīva translated it into Chinese. They completed two third of the text when Puṇyatara became ill and suddenly left the world. As the great enterprise remained unfinished and the master died, everyone was deeply distressed to a degree that went beyond ordinary grief.

3. Dharmaruci 曇摩流支

Dharmaruci means Joy of the Dharma. He was a native of the Western Regions. He gave up his family and entered the Way. He attained great fame purely due to being proficient in the Vinaya-piṭaka. In the autumn of the seventh year of the Hongshi reign (405) he arrived in Guanzhong. At first, Dharmaruci recited and translated the *Shisong* but died before finishing it.

Shi Huiyuan of Mount Lu had heard of Dharmaruci's excellence in the vinaya and, hoping to obtain a complete Vinaya-piṭaka, sent a letter to him with friendly intentions, saying: "The teachings of the Buddha first spread in your esteemed country and it has been over four hundred years since it also spread elsewhere. Yet with respect to the moral rules of the śramaṇa, there are still many deficiencies. Recently, master Puṇyatara of the Western Regions, a native of Kashmir, recited the *fan* version the *Shisong* and dharma master Kumārajīva, a man of great talent and knowledge, translated it. In their work on the *Shisong*, they translated more than half of the text when Puṇyatara prematurely died. He fell into eternal sleep halfway through his path, not being able to finish his great enterprise. We regretted this bitterly! But I have heard that Your Kindness brought this sutra with you, which made me extremely happy. This must be a coincidence brought about by fate, rather than the doing of men! In my opinion, the dissemination of the teaching among the people is a task that has to be carried out in accordance with the circumstances. When someone is imploring us, we should not hold back ourselves. If you can finish this sutra for the benefit of those studying the Vinaya, you would elucidate the pure practices and wash clean their ears and eyes. This would allow those who have just stepped into the stream not to overlook the supreme ford and those who are already partaking in the excellent enterprise to shine brighter than the sun and the moon.⁴ On your part this would be a profoundly benevolent and extremely meritorious act that would move men and spirits alike. I hope my request does not go completely against your intentions 垂懷不乖往意一二.⁵ But these are things you know yourself."

Having received Huiyuan's letter and Yao Xing's earnest invitation, Dharmaruci, together with Kumārajīva, completed the translation of the entire *Shisong*. They carefully studied and analyzed the text, examining and fixing its structure. Kumārajīva, however, was still unsatisfied with the translation, thinking that it was cumbersome and imperfect. Soon after this, Kumārajīva passed away without having revised the text.

Dharmaruci lived in the Dasi 大寺 monastery in Chang'an. Huiguan 慧觀 wanted to invite him to the capital (i.e. Jiankang) but Dharmaruci said: "That place has men and has the dharma, thus there is enough to benefit the world. I should rather travel to places where the teaching of Vinaya is not yet present." Accordingly, he travelled to teach in other regions. There is nothing known of his death. Some say that he passed away in the region of Liangzhou but this is unconfirmed.

⁴ The Japanese, Russian and French translators all think that the phrase 'victorious enterprise' here refers to the translation job. While this is certainly a possibility, I think that since such people are placed and parallel location and in contrast with beginners, it is more likely that the phrase refers to the act monastic observance. In other words, those just stepping into the stream are contrasted with those already well on their way.

⁵ The Zhonghua shuju edition parses the text in a way that puts the *yi'er* at the end of the previous sentence.

4. Vimalākṣa (Bimoluocha 卑摩羅叉)

Vimalākṣa means Immaculate Eye. He was a native of Kashmir and was a calm person with a strong will power. When he became a monk and stepped on the Way, he devoted himself to the practice of austerity.

Formerly, Vimalākṣa had taught the Vinaya-piṭaka at Kucha and scholars of the four corners competed in calling him their teacher. At the time, Kumārajīva was also among them. When Kucha fell, Vimalākṣa fled the region. After a while, he heard that Kumārajīva was widely propagating the Sūtra-piṭaka in Chang'an and wished that the excellent texts of the Vinaya spread again the Eastern Kingdom (i.e. China). Therefore, he took his staff and disregarding the dangers of the Drifting Sands, travelled to the East.

In the eighth year of the Hongshi reign (408) of the illegitimate [i.e. Later] Qin dynasty, Vimalākṣa he arrived in the Guanzhong region where Kumārajīva venerated him with the rites of the master. Vimalākṣa was also very happy to see him after such a long time. When Kumārajīva died, Vimalākṣa went on a journey to the east of Guanzhong. He stopped in Shouchun 壽春 and stayed at the Shijian monastery 石澗寺. Students of the Discipline flocked to him and he comprehensively explicated the Vinaya for them.

The *Shisong* translated by Vimalākṣa comprises fifty-eight *juan*. The last section explains the rules of the acceptance of precepts and the various ways of accomplishing good dharma. Based on its general content, this section was named “Good Recitation.” Vimalākṣa later brought the whole text to the Shijian monastery and expanded it into sixty-one *juan*, changing the last section into “Recitation on the Vinaya.” This is why there are still two names for it.

Later on, Vimalākṣa travelled south to Jiangling 江陵 and spend his summer retreat at the Xinsi 辛寺 monastery, lecturing on the *Shisong*. Knowing Chinese very well, he was very good at teaching others. At the time, he broadly explicated this marvellous work on ‘non-action’ 無作.⁶ Those who were interested in the text and its meaning gathered around him like trees in a forest. Equally numerous were those who understood the articles and the prohibitions. The wide spread of the Vinaya is the result of Vimalākṣa’s efforts.

Huiguan 慧觀 of the Daochang 道場 monastery has been trying to attain the main objective of Vimalākṣa’s teachings. He recorded the inner prohibitions stipulated by him according to their strictness, compiling a work in two *juan*. He sent this back to the capital where the monks and nuns were began learning it, competing to make copies of it. At the time those who heard about this, composed a little quatrain about it:

Vimalākṣa’s unrefined words
Huiguan recorded in a brilliant manner;
People of the capital copy it so much
That paper is as expensive as jade.

⁶ See Funayama’s comment.

Copies made at that time are still in circulation, serving as a model for later students.

Vimalākṣa cultivated his merits and loved seclusion; he left behind the bustle and hubbub of the world. In the winter of that same year, he returned to the Shijian monastery in Shouchun and died there. He was seventy-seven years old. Vimalākṣa had blue eyes so the people also called him Blue-eyed Vinaya Master.

5. Buddhayaśas (Fotuoyeshe 佛陀耶舍)

Buddhayaśas means Glory of the Awakened One. He was a native of Kashmir, coming from a Brahmin clan who for generations had been following a heterodox faith. When a śramaṇa begged food from his family, his father flew into rage and hit him. Following this, his father's arms and legs were seized by convulsions and the extent that he could not move. Thereupon, they sought advice from a sorcerer who told them: "This is caused by the spirits because you have insulted a virtuous man." Then they invited the śramaṇa into their home and wholeheartedly repented. In a few days, the father recovered. Because of this, he told Buddhayaśas to become a monk and be the śramaṇa's disciple. At the time, Buddhayaśas was thirteen years old. He often followed his teacher on distant journeys and once in the wilderness they came across a tiger. The teacher wanted to escape but Buddhayaśas said: "This tiger is already full, it will certainly not attack a human." Suddenly, the tiger left and, as they moved forward, they indeed came across remains of its prey. The teacher secretly felt admiration towards him.

By the time Buddhayaśas was fifteen years old, he could recite twenty-thirty thousand words of sutras. Because in the monastery he lived monks usually had to go outside to beg, he was falling behind in his recitation. But an Arhat who valued his intelligence highly often shared the food he had begged with him. By the age of nineteen, he could recite several millions words from Mahayana and Hinayana sutras. He was, however, proud by nature and was especially vain about his vast knowledge, claiming that there were very few of those who could be his teachers. For this reason, he was not respected by other monks. Still, since he had an attractive look and was good at pleasant conversation, those who came to see him forgot their deep-rooted resentment.

When he reached the age of accepting the precepts, there was no one to conduct the ceremony. For this reason, even when he was already an adult, he was still a śrāmaṇera. Consequently, he learned from his maternal uncle the treatises of the Five Sciences (*Pañcavidyāsthāna*) and has studied many of the arts and skills of the world. It was only at the age of twenty-seven that he received the precepts in their entirety. At all times, he took reading and recitation as his primary task, his hands never let go off the manuscript tablets. He often sat straight thinking about the meaning of the texts, and was unaware of having missed his noon meal. This is how great his concentration was!

Later Buddhayaśas travelled to the kingdom of Kashgar. The king Buyu 不忭 invited together three thousand monks and Buddhayaśas was one of these. At the time, the crown prince Dharmaputra 達摩弗多, whose name means the Son of the Dharma, seeing that Buddhayaśas's face and clothes were elegant and refined, asked where he had come from. Buddhayaśas's response was clear and eloquent. The crown prince liked him and even invited him to remain in

the palace to *gongyang*, providing for him lavishly. Later Kumārajīva came there and studied with Buddhayaśas again, treating him with great respect. When Kumārajīva followed his mother back to Kucha, Buddhayaśas stayed behind.

Shortly after that, the king died and the crown prince succeeded him on the throne. At this time Fu Jian sent Lü Guang on a military expedition to the west against Kucha. The king of Kucha urgently sought help from Kashgar and so the king of Kashgar himself led an army to the rescue. He asked Buddhayaśas to stay behind and aid the crown prince, putting him in charge of the rear. Kucha fell before the rescue forces arrived. The king returned and told Buddhayaśas that Kumārajīva had been seized by Lü Guang. Buddhayaśas sighed and said: “Although Kumārajīva and I have met a long time ago, we have not exhausted our ideas. Now that he has suddenly become a prisoner, when will I see him again!”

Buddhayaśas stayed in Kashgar for ten years. After that, he went east to Kucha where he exerted himself in teaching the dharma. At that time Kumārajīva was in Guzang and Buddhayaśas sent a letter with an invitation. He packed his provisions and was about to depart but the people of the kingdom [of Kucha] did not let him leave. Thus he stayed about another year. Later Buddhayaśas said to one of his disciples: “I want to find Kumārajīva. Prepare for the trip in secret, we will leave at night so that nobody knows about it.” The disciple said: “I am afraid that they will catch us the very next day and we cannot avoid being taken back.” Buddhayaśas then took a bowl full of clean water and put some medicine in it. He uttered a spell several dozen words long and washed his feet together with the disciple. They left during the same night and by daybreak had travelled several hundred *li*. Buddhayaśas asked the disciple: “What do you feel?” The disciple replied: “I can only hear the sound of the strong wind and feel the tears flowing from my eyes.” Buddhayaśas and the disciple washed their feet again with charmed water and stopped to rest. When the following morning the people of the country went in their pursuit, they had been hundreds of *li* ahead and so they could not be caught. By the time they reached Guzang, Kumārajīva had already went to Chang’an. Hearing that Yao Xing forced him to live with concubines and urges him to go against the teaching, Buddhayaśas sighed and said: “Kumārajīva is like a fine brocade, how can one throw him into the thorny thicket?” Having heard that Buddhayaśas arrived in Guzang, Kumārajīva advised Yao Xing to meet him but Yao Xing did not listen to him.

After a while Yao Xing ordered Kumārajīva to translate the Sūtra-piṭaka. Kumārajīva said: “Now for the propagation of the teaching of dharma, one should make the text’s style and meaning be in perfect accord. I have not yet mastered this art, only Buddhayaśas has a profound understanding of this abstruse principle. He is currently in Guzang, please issue an order to summon him. When one checks every word three times and only then writes it down, then even subtle nuances are not lost and the text remains trustworthy for a thousand years. Yao Xing consented to this and sent a messenger to invite Buddhayaśas over. He presented him with generous gifts but Buddhayaśas did not accept any of these. Then he laughed and said: “Since an imperial order has been brought to me, I should hasten there. My benefactor is very generous to people but if he treats me as he did Kumārajīva, I will not dare to obey his order.” The messenger returned and reported everything. Yao Xing praised Buddhayaśas’s caution and sent another invitation with detailed instructions. Only then did Buddhayaśas come to Chang’an. Yao Xing came out to greet him. He erected a separate residence for him inside Xiaoyao Park, and

supplied him with the four provisions. Buddhayaśas did not accept any of these. He begged for alms at the prescribed time and had only one meal a day.

At this time Kumārajīva translated the *Shizhu jing*. He struggled and vacillated over it for more than a month but could not commit to a written form. Once Buddhayaśas arrived, they arrived together at solutions and only then were the literary style and their inner sense fixed. Over three thousand monks and laymen admired their accuracy and succinctness.

Buddhayaśas had a red moustache and because he had a thorough understanding of the Abhidharma-vibhāṣa-śāstra, people at the time called him Red-Moustached Vibhāṣa 赤髭毘婆沙. Since he was Kumārajīva's teacher, they also called him Great Vibhāṣa 大毘婆沙. The four provisions presented to him, including robes, begging bowls and bedding, filled three buildings but he paid no attention to them. Yao Xing sold them off and [using the money] built a monastery in the southern part of the city.

Earlier on, Buddhayaśas was reciting the *Tanwudelü* 曇無德律 (Dharmaguptavinaya) and metropolitan commandant (*sili jiaowei* 司隸校尉) Yao Shuang 姚爽 asked him to translate it. But Yao Xing, suspicious of potential omissions and mistakes, asked Buddhayaśas to memorize and recite a register of the Qiang 羌 people and a collection of medical recipes, totalling about fifty-thousand words. After two days, he held the text in hand 執文 and reproduced it without a single mistake. Everyone was in awe of his extraordinary memory. Thus in the twelfth year of the Hongshi reign (410) he published the *Sifenlü* 四分律 in a total of forty-four *juan*, the *Chang Ahan* 長阿含 and other texts. Śramaṇa Zhu Fonian from Liangzhou was translating orally into Chinese and Daohan held the brush. The enterprise ended in the fifteenth year (413) of the same reign. Yao Xing gave Buddhayaśas a donation of ten thousand bolts of silk but he did not accept it. He also donated to Daohan and Zhu Fonian a thousand bolts of silk each, and gave generous donations to each of the five hundred eminent śramaṇa.

Later Buddhayaśas bid farewell and returned to foreign lands. He went to Kashmir where he obtained a copy of the *Xukongzang jing* 虛空藏經 in one *juan*. He entrusted it to a merchant to take it to the monastic community in Liangzhou. Nothing is known of his death.

6. Buddhahadra (Fotuobatuoluo 佛馱跋陀羅)

Buddhabhadra means Excellence of the Awakened One. His original surname was Shi 釋, he was a native of Kapilavastu 迦維羅衛, a descendant of king Amṛtōdana. His paternal grandfather Dharmadeva 達摩提婆, whose name means God of the Law, was once a travelling merchant in Northern India, which is why Buddhahadra also lived there. His father Dharmasūrya 達摩修耶利, whose name means Sun of the Law, died when he was still a child. Buddhahadra was left without a father at the age of three and from there on lived with his mother. At the age of five, he also lost his mother and was raised by another family. His grandfather's brother Jiupoli 鳩婆利 (Kuvalaya?) heard of his intelligence and was, also pitying that he was an orphan, took him back and made him become a śramaṇera.

When he was seventeen years old, along with several of his fellow students, he was fully immersed in learning and reciting texts from memory. Whatever took others one month, Buddhahadra could fully memorize in a day. His teacher sighed and said: “Buddhabhadra overcomes thirty rivals a day!” When he received full ordination, he became focussed on self-cultivation. He widely studied the sutras and most of them understood completely.

Since an early age, he was well known for his mastery of meditation and the vinaya. He often travelled to Kashmir with his fellow student Saṃghadatta 僧伽達多, with whom he stayed together for years. Even though Saṃghadatta acknowledged his talent and acumen, he did not appreciate him as a person. At one time, he sat in meditation in a hidden cave behind closed doors when he saw Buddhahadra coming. Surprised, he asked him: “How did you come there?” Buddhahadra replied: “For a moment, I went to Tuṣita Heaven to pay homage to Maitreya.” Having finished speaking, he instantly disappeared. Saṃghadatta realized that he was a holy person whose depth he has not fathomed. Later on, he saw Buddhahadra’s miraculous transformation on several occasions and reverentially asked him about this. Only then did he realize that Buddhahadra had obtained the realization of non-returner.

Buddhabhadra often wanted to travel to distant lands to teach and to observe in detail their customs. Just at that time, there was śramaṇa Zhiyan 智嚴 from the Qin state who came west to Kashmir. Seeing how splendid the dharma assembly there was, he looked back to the East and said with deep feelings: “My fellow practitioners are devoted to the Way, yet they have not met a true master and so they do not have a pathway to enlightenment!” Thereupon he enquired from the local saṃgha who could spread the teaching to the East. They said: “There is someone called Buddhahadra, who was born in the city of Nagahara(?) 那呵利. For generations, his clan followed the teaching. He became a monk at a tender age and acquired a profound understanding of the sutras and sastras. When he was still young, he received the precepts from the great dhyāna master Buddhasena 佛大先.” At the time, Buddhasena was also in Kashmir and said to Zhiyan: “Buddhabhadra is indeed the one who can stir and support monks and their followers, who spread and teach methods of meditation.”

Zhiyan tried hard to convince Buddhahadra to accept his invitation and in the end he took pity on him and consented. Thus he parted from the local saṃgha and said goodbye to his master, packed provisions and went east. He travelled for three years, experienced extended periods of cold and heat, crossed the Pamir and passed through the Six Kingdoms where the rulers appreciated his coming to teach from afar and wholeheartedly gave offerings.

In Jiaozhi 交趾 (today’s Northern Vietnam), he boarded a boat and sailed along the coast. When they were passing by an island, Buddhahadra pointed at the mountain and said: “We should stop here.” The owner of the boat said: “Time is dear when travelling and it is hard to ride the spring wind. We cannot stop.” They sailed for more than two hundred *li* when suddenly the wind turned around and blew the boat back to the island. This is when the people in the boat realized his miraculous power. Everyone treated him as their master and listened to his commands. Afterwards, they had favourable wind and the other boats all departed. But Buddhahadra said: “We must not leave.” Thus the owner of the boat stayed in one place. In a little while, those boats that had left early, all sank at the same time. Later on, in the middle of the night he suddenly asked the remaining boats to all depart. Nobody would agree to this. Then

Buddhabhadra pulled the mooring rope up himself and their boat left alone. Suddenly, pirates came and everyone who stayed there was robbed and harmed.

In a while, he arrived at Donglai commandery 東萊郡 in Qingzhou 青州. Hearing that Kumārajīva was in Chang'an, he went there to see him. Kumārajīva was overjoyed and the two of them discussed the characteristics of the dharma and uncovered its hidden nuances, leading to a number of realizations. Thereupon Buddhabhadra asked Kumārajīva: "What you explain does not go beyond ordinary human understanding, yet you have reached great fame. Why is that?" Kumārajīva replied: "It is simply because I am old. Why need is there to be praised?" Every time Kumārajīva had doubts about the meaning of a passage, he would always consult with Buddhabhadra.

At the time Yao Hong, the crown prince of the Qin wanted to hear Buddhabhadra expound the dharma. Therefore, he ordered the monks to gather for a discussion in the Eastern Palace 東宮. Kumārajīva and Buddhabhadra went through several rounds of questions and answers. Kumārajīva asked: "Why are dharmas empty?" Buddhabhadra replied: "The multitude of particles make up matter but matter has no nature on its own. This is why even though it is matter, it is empty." Kumārajīva asked again: "Since you use minute particles to destroy the emptiness of matter, how would you then destroy the particle?" Buddhabhadra replied: "Some masters dissect a single particle but I am of a different opinion." Kumārajīva asked again: "Are particles permanent?" Buddhabhadra answered: "It is because of a single particle that the many particles are empty, it is because of the many particles that a single particle is empty." At the time Baoyun 寶雲 translated these words without understanding their meaning. Both monks and lay believers all thought that what Buddhabhadra formulated was the permanence of the minute particles.

On another day, the monk exegetes of Chang'an invited Buddhabhadra to explain things again. Buddhabhadra said: "Now the dharmas are not born spontaneously as a result of the coming together of various conditions. It is because of one particle that there are the many particles. A particle does not have a nature on its own, which is precisely why it is empty! So we should rather speak of the non-destruction of a single particle. Isn't it permanent and not empty?" This is the general sense of the debate.

The Qin ruler Yao Xing was fully devoted to the Buddha's teaching. He supported over three thousand monks who often came to the palace and were deeply involved with worldly affairs. Only Buddhabhadra maintained his tranquility and stayed away from the crowd. Afterwards, he told his disciple: "Yesterday I saw that five boats from my hometown sailed off together." Soon the disciple related the story to outsiders and the orthodox monks of the Guanzhong region all thought that Buddhabhadra was trying to present himself as an eccentric to fool others.

Buddhabhadra widely propagated the dhyāna in Chang'an. Those who found joy in calmness flocked to him from the four directions as soon as they heard about this. But they differed to what extent they were dedicated to studying and how advanced they were in the teaching. There were also hypocrites who deceived others. There was a disciple who, on account of having done a little bit of contemplation practice, said of himself that he had attained the realization of non-returner (*anāgāmin*). Buddhabhadra has not immediately tested him, which led to rumours that

slandered him maliciously and claimed that unforeseen disasters were imminent. Therefore the followers either concealed their names and hid away or climbed through the monastery wall and fled in the night. Within half a day, almost all of them scattered. Yet Buddhahadra remained calm and unconcerned. At the time, conservative monks, such as Senglüe and Daoheng, told Buddhahadra: “Even the Buddha did not allow one to talk about the dharma attained. And your earlier story about the five boats which were supposed to be coming was untrue and had no reality. Also, your followers are swindlers who give rise to dissent. Since these things violate the Discipline, according to the rules you may not stay with us. You should immediately leave, do not remain here!” Buddhahadra said: “My body is like floating duckweed, it is very easy for me to leave or stay. I only regret that I have not expressed all of my ideas. What a shame!”

Therefore, he left together with his disciple Huiguan and more than forty other followers. He was in a calm state of mind and his face revealed no changes. Those who knew the truth [about his departure] all felt regretful. There were over a thousand monks and lay followers seeing him off. Yao Xing was saddened by his departure. He said to Daoheng: “Śramaṇa Buddhahadra travelled here to bring the Way to us, wanting to spread the teachings left behind by the Buddha. He has not yet divulged everything, which is deeply lamentable! How can we make ten thousand people lose their guidance because of one word of blame!” Thus he sent a messenger to bring him back. But Buddhahadra said to the messenger: “I am sincerely aware of the favour His Majesty bestows on me but I cannot obey his order.” Thus he led his companions in nightly marches in a southward direction towards the peaks of Mount Lu.

Śramaṇa Shi Huiyuan knew of Buddhahadra for a long time. Hearing of his coming, he was overjoyed as if seeing an old friend. Huiyuan thought that Buddhahadra’s expulsion was the fault of his disciple and that if he had made a prediction about the five boats, this was merely a matter of believing in it, but it did not violate the Discipline. He then sent his disciple Tanyong 曇邕 to deliver a letter to Yao Xing and the monks of Guanzhong, offering a solution to the issue of expulsion. He then also asked Buddhahadra to publish several texts concerning the calculations of the dhyāna.

Buddhahadra’s mind was set on travelling and teaching, he did not seek the comfort of long-term residence. He stayed [at Mount Lu] for only about a year when he travelled west again, to Jiangling. There he witnessed the arrival of foreign boats. Straightaway, he made enquiries and they turned out to be those five boats from India which he had seen [in his vision] before. Officials and commoners from the entire region competed in paying him respect. He did not accept any of the gifts presented to him; instead, he went on his begging rounds with his alms bowl, not caring whether someone was of rich or lowly status.

At that time Yuan Bao 袁豹 of Chen commandery 陳郡 was an aide to the defender-in-chief, [the future] Emperor Wu 武帝 (363-422, r. 420-422) of the Song. When [the future] Emperor Wu conquered Liu Yi 劉毅 (d. 412) in the south, Yuan Bao followed him until they arrived in Jiangling. Buddhahadra along with his disciple Huiguan visited Yuan Bao and begged for food. Yuan Bao had never believed [in the dharma] and so he treated Huiguan very meagerly. Without having eaten to his fill, they excused themselves and retreated but Yuan Bao said: “It seems that you have not had enough. Please stay a little longer.” Buddhahadra said: “Your generosity, oh donor, is limited. This is why you let what has been served to be exhausted.” Yuan Bao

immediately sent an attendant to bring more rice but it turned out to have been all used up. This made him greatly ashamed. In a little while he asked Huiguan: “What kind of person is this śramaṇa?” Huiguan replied: “His merits are so high that a layman cannot fathom them.” Yuan Bao was in awe of Buddhahadra and told about him the defender-in-chief, who asked him to meet. He venerated Buddhahadra greatly and offered him gifts. In a short while, when the defender-in-chief had to return to the capital, he asked Buddhahadra to accompany him and set him up at the Daochang monastery 道場寺.

Buddhahadra’s etiquette revolved around categorical simplicity, which is different from Chinese custom. His intents were pure and far-reaching, sophisticated and having a profound purpose. A dharma master Sengbi 僧弼 from the capital, in a letter to śramaṇa Baolin 寶林, wrote: “The dhyāna master of Douchang 鬪場 (i.e. Buddhahadra) possesses the great boddhi-mind. He is also a distinguished man of letters, an Indian Wang Bi 王弼 (226-249) or He Yan 何晏 (ca. 195-249)!” This is how others praised him.

Prior to this, śramaṇa Zhi Faling 支法領 obtained in Khotan the beginning part of the *Huayan jing* (Avatamsaka sūtra) in thirty-six thousand gathas, none of which had been promulgated and translated before. In the fourteenth year of the Yixi reign (418), Meng Yi 孟顛 (fl. first half of 5th century), internal administrator of Wujun 吳郡 commandery, and right guard general Chu Shudu 褚叔度 (378-424) invited Buddhahadra to serve as a master of translation. Thus he held the *fan* text and, together with more than a hundred śramaṇas, including Faye 法業 and Huiyan 慧嚴, translated and published the text at the Daochang [monastery]. They determined the wording and the general aim of the text, making the Chinese and foreign versions thoroughly in accord. They captured the meaning of the sutra flawlessly. For this reason, the Daochang monastery still has an Avatamsaka Hall.

In addition, śramaṇa Faxian 法顯 obtained a *fan* manuscript of the *Sengqilü* 僧祇律 (*Sāṃghikāvinaya*) and asked Buddhahadra to translate it into Chinese. This is related in the biography of Faxian. Altogether he published a total of fifteen titles in hundred and seventeen *juan*, including the *Guanfo sanmei hai* 觀佛三昧海 in six *juan*, *Niyuan* 泥洹 and *Xiuxing fangbian lun* 修行方便論. He always probed into the deepest aims of the original and could superbly attain the sense of the text.

Buddhahadra died in the sixth year of the Yuanjia 元嘉 reign (429), at the age of seventy-one.

7. Dharmakṣema (Tanwuchen 曇無讖第)

The name Dharmakṣema is also written as Tanmochan 曇摩讖 or Tanwuchan 曇無讖, as the *fan* sound can be transliterated in different way. He was originally a native of Middle India. He lost his father at the age of six and together with his mother wove carpets for a living. He met the śramaṇa Dharmayaśas, whose name means Glory of the Law, and who was esteemed and given gifts by both monks and laymen. Dharmakṣema’s mother regarded him highly and gave her son to him as a disciple. At the age of ten, he was reciting spells with several of his fellow students,

but excelled among them in terms of intelligence. Reciting sutras, he could memorize over ten thousand words a day. Initially, he studied the Hīnayāna but at the same time also read the theories of the five fields of knowledge (see above). In preaching and debating, there was no one who could match him. Afterwards, he met dhyāna master Baitou 白頭 and the two engaged in a debate. Since they had different training, the debate continued for ten ten-day intervals. Even though Dharmakṣema's attacks were piercing, the dhyāna master would never yield. Dharmakṣema acknowledged the sophistication of his reasoning and asked him: "Would you have the scripture [you mention]? Could I look at it?" The dhyāna master thus gave him a manuscript of the *Niepan jing* 涅槃經 (*Nirvāṇa sūtra*) written on tree bark. Dharmakṣema quickly read through it and was astonished, feeling ashamed that for being so narrow-minded,⁷ for a long time being confused about the great Vaipulya texts. Therefore he gathered his fellow students and repented his mistake, and from there on devoted himself to the Mahāyāna. At the age of twenty, he had memorized over two million words from both Mahāyāna and Hīnayāna sutras.

Dharmakṣema's cousin was an expert in training elephants. As he rode it, he [accidentally] killed the king's great elephant white ears. The king was enraged and had him executed, issuing an order: "If someone dares to look at him, I will kill him and his closest relatives." The parents did not dare to visit the body but Dharmakṣema mourned and buried him. The king was enraged and wanted to execute Dharmakṣema but he said: "Your Majesty killed him according to the law. I buried him according to the familial duty and this does not violate the great justice. Why would you be angry?" All those present froze from fear but Dharmakṣema's expression remained calm and at ease. The king was amazed by his resolute will and consequently asked him to stay, offering him gifts.

Dharmakṣema was highly skilled in the art of spells, whatever he applied this art to was always substantiated. In the Western Regions, people called him the Great Spell Master. Once he accompanied the king into the mountains. The king was thirsty but there was no water. Thereupon Dharmakṣema secretly uttered a spell and a rock issued forth water. He then praised the king: "The great king's benevolence produced a miracle, causing this barren rock give forth a spring!" The neighbouring countries heard about this and all admired the king's virtue. At the time rains fell in a timely manner and the people sang songs of joy. The king loved his magic arts and became even more fond of him.

After some time the king's goodwill slightly weakened and his generosity gradually slackened. Dharmakṣema realized that it was his prolonged stay that led to a change in attitude, hence he left and went to Kashmir. He took with him the first part of the *Nirvāṇa sūtra* in ten *juan*, the *Pusa ji jing* 菩薩戒經, *Pusa jieben* 菩薩戒本 and others. In that country (i.e. Kashmir) most people study the Hīnayāna and do not believe in nirvana. He thus went east to Kucha. After a while he went farther to Guzang, where he stayed in a postal inn. Concerned that he would lose the sutra manuscripts, he used them as a pillow when sleeping but someone pulled them onto the ground. Dharmakṣema awoke with a start, thinking that it was a thief. This happened on three nights in a row, until he heard a voice coming out of nowhere: "These are the treasure of the

⁷ Lit. 'had a knowledge of a well-bottom', a reference to the story of the frog sitting at the bottom of the well, only seeing a small segment of the sky.

liberation of the Tathāgata, why would you use them as a pillow?” Therefore Dharmakṣema felt ashamed and placed them on a high place. During the night, there were thieves who tried to lift them several times but in the end were unable to do so. In the morning, when Dharmakṣema picked them up to leave, they did not seem heavy to him. The thieves saw this and considered him a sage. They all came to pay their respect and apologize.

Juqu Mengsun 沮渠蒙遜, Prince of Hexi 河西, seized the region of Liangzhou and declared himself a king. Having heard about Dharmakṣema’s fame, he called him over for a personal meeting, treating him with great generosity. Juqu Mengsun venerated the great teaching and was devoted to spreading it. He wanted Dharmakṣema to publish his texts. Since he had not learned the local language and there were no other translators, Dharmakṣema was afraid that he would make errors in the logic of the text and did not give his consent right away. Accordingly, he studied the language for three years and only then translated and wrote down the first part [of the *Nirvāṇa sūtra*] in ten *juan*.

At this time śramaṇas Huisong 慧嵩 and Daolang 道朗 were the most prominent monks in Hexi. As Dharmakṣema was translating and publishing 宣出 the *Sūtra-piṭaka*, they held his work in high esteem. As the *fan* text was converted into Chinese, Huisong held the brush. Hundreds of monks and layman asked difficult questions on all sorts of topics. Dharmakṣema faced the problems and resolved the obstacles with fluent eloquence. At the same time, the translation was rich in literary embellishments, with beautiful and dense expressions.

Huisong, Daolang and others also asked him to publish many more sutras. He next translated the *Daji* 大集, *Dayun* 大雲, *Beihua* 悲華, *Dichi* 地持, *Youposa jie* 優婆塞戒, *Jinguangming* 金光明, *Hailongwang* 海龍王, *Pusa jieben* 菩薩戒本 and others, in total amounting to over six-hundred thousand words. Dharmakṣema thought that some chapters were missing from the *Niepan jing* (*Nirvāṇa sūtra*) so when he returned to his native country, he tried to find these. Just at this moment his mother died and thus he remained there for over a year. Later in Khotan he obtained the second part of the sutra, which he translated when he returned to Guzang. Afterwards, he sent a messenger to Khotan to locate the last part of the sutra, which was subsequently translated into Chinese in thirty-three *juan*. The translation began in the third year of the illegitimate Xuanshi 玄始 reign (414) and the three bundles were completed on the twenty-third day of the tenth month of the tenth year of the Xuanshi reign (421), which corresponds to the second year of the Yongchu 永初 reign of Emperor Wu of the Song dynasty. Dharmakṣema said: “The *fan* version of this sutra originally consisted of thirty-five thousand gathas, which is just under a million words. Now the translated version has only a bit over ten thousand gathas.”

Dharmakṣema once told Juqu Mengsun: “Demons entered the city, there will inevitably be many disasters and diseases. Juqu Mengsun did not believe him and wanted to see for himself so that he could verify his words. Dharmakṣema then applied his magic onto Juqu Mengsun who now saw the demons and was terrified. Dharmakṣema said: “I should undergo sincere purification and then use a divine spell to drive them away.” With this, he recited spells for three days, then said to Juqu Mengsun: “The demons are now gone!” Around this time there were people on the border who saw the demons and said: “We saw several hundred disease-causing demons

escaping until they were gone.” The entire land became peaceful and this was the result of Dharmakṣema’s effort. From there on, Juqu Mengsun revered him even more.

In the second year of the Juqu Mengsun’s illegitimate Chengxuan 承玄 reign (429), Juqu Mengsun crossed the Yellow River to attack Qifu Mumo 乞伏暮末 at Baohan 抱罕. He sent his crown prince Xingguo 興國 ahead as a vanguard but he was defeated and captured by Qifu Mumo’s forces. Later the Qifu fell and Qifu Mumo along with Xingguo were taken by Helian Dingding 赫連定, who was in turn later destroyed by the Tuyuhun. Xingguo was subsequently killed by rebels. Juqu Mengsun was enraged and claimed that his reverence of the Buddha had no effect. Thus he expelled the śramaṇas and ordered those under the age of fifty to give up the Way. Earlier, Juqu Mengsun had erected for his mother a stone statue six *zhang* in height.⁸ Now the statue was shedding tears. Dharmakṣema used wise words to deliver his remonstrations and so Juqu Mengsun changed his mind and regretted his earlier behaviour.

At this time the Wei barbarian Tuoba Dao 託跋燾, having heard that Dharmakṣema possessed the art of magic, sent a messenger with an invitation. He informed Juqu Mengsun: “If you do not send Dharmakṣema to me, I will immediately go against you with my army.” Juqu Mengsun had already venerated Dharmakṣema for a long time and could not bear letting him go. Later Tuoba Dao again sent Li Shun 李順, Chamberlain for Ceremonial and Duke of Gaoping 高平公, to appoint Juqu Mengsun to Commissioned with Extraordinary Powers Area Commander-in-Chief of Liangzhou; Area Commander of the Western Regions; Grand Mentor Cavalry General-in-Chief; Regional Governor of Liangzhou; and Prince of Liang. In addition, he conferred on him the nine imperial gifts and issued the following order: “I have heard that you have in your presence dharma master Dharmakṣema, who is as widely learned and knowledgeable as Kumārajīva and as skilled in achieving miraculous effects with secret spells as Venerable Fotudeng 佛圖澄. I want him to lecture on the Way here, send him to me by mounted couriers!”

Juqu Mengsun entertained Li Shun at a banquet above the Xinle Gates 新樂門. He said to Li Shun: “I, Juqu Mengsun, is an old subject in the Western Regions and serve the court without ever daring to disobey. However, you, the Son of Heaven, gave credit to the words of flatterers and coerces me. Earlier I have deferentially requested to leave Dharmakṣema with me but this time you demand him again. He is my own master and I will die with him. I honestly do not mind about dying prematurely. A man dies only once in his lifetime, but he knows not when!”

Li Shun replied: “Your sincerity is already known, you have sent your beloved son to serve at the court. The court admires your loyal achievements and has graciously conferred upon you special favours. Yet you are ready to overturn a mountain of accomplishments for the sake of this one barbarian monk! I cannot bear to see that you destroy all the benefits of the future because of one day’s anger.⁹ Is this how you pay back the court’s generosity? I do not commend this! The ruler is extremely open-minded, this is something also known to Hongwen 弘文.” Hongwen was the envoy Juqu Mengsun sent to the Wei court.

⁸ The characters *zhang* and *liu* seem to be inverted.

⁹ Both Robert Shih and Yermakov seem to misunderstand this sentence.

Juqu Mengsun said: “You, Chamberlain for Ceremonial, are just as much an expert with words as Su Qin 蘇秦. But I am afraid your words do not match the situation.” Juqu Mengsun had become so attached to Dharmakṣema that he could not let him go. Moreover, he also feared that the Wei would become too powerful.

In the third month of the third year of the Juqu Mengsun’s Yihe 義和 reign (433), Dharmakṣema asked permission to travel west again in search of the last part of the *Nirvāṇa sūtra*. Juqu Mengsun was angry that he wanted to leave and thus secretly plotted to kill him. He pretended to provide him provisions for the road, lavishly presenting him with jewels and goods. On the day of his departure, Dharmakṣema told everyone with tears in his eyes: “My time of karmic retribution is coming, none of the saints can save me!” Because he had originally made a vow, his sense of duty would not tolerate him staying. When he departed, Juqu Mengsun indeed sent an assassin who killed him on the road. He was forty-nine years old. This year corresponded to the tenth year of the Yuanjia reign (433) of the Song dynasty. Monks and laymen from near and far all mourned him together. After a while the attendants of Juqu Mengsun started seeing demons and spirits in broad daylight, attacking him with swords. In the fourth month, fell ill and died.

Initially, when Dharmakṣema lived in Guzang, the śramaṇa Daojin 道進 from Zhangye 張掖 wanted to receive the bodhisattva precepts from him. Dharmakṣema said: “Confess your transgressions!” Thus Daojin wholeheartedly did this for seven days and seven nights, and on the eighth day went to see Dharmakṣema and asked him for the precepts. But Dharmakṣema suddenly flew into a rage. Daojin thought: “It simply must be that my karmic obstacles have not been eliminated yet.” So he concentrated his efforts for three years, doing both meditation and confession. Once when he was in meditation, he saw that Śākyamuni Buddha along with other great beings conferred on him the vinaya teachings. That night there were over ten people staying in the same place and they all dreamt what he saw. Daojin went to see Dharmakṣema to tell him about this. When he was only a few dozen steps away, Dharmakṣema rose up in surprise and exclaimed: “Excellent indeed! You have already obtained the precepts! I will still be your witness.” Then he successively explained to him in front of the image of the Buddha the state of precepts.

At this time the śramaṇa Daolang enjoyed great fame in the region west of the Pass. The night when Daojin obtained the precepts, Daolang also saw the dream. Thereupon disregarding the number of years he had been ordained himself, he asked Daojin to take him as his disciple. Consequently, there were over a thousand people who followed Daojin and obtain ordination from him. These rules are transmitted even now but they all originate from Dharmakṣema.

There is also a different record that claims: “The *Pusa dichī jing* had to be brought to these lands by Yibole (Īśvara?) Bodhisattva 伊波勒菩薩. Later it was in fact Dharmakṣema who transmitted and translated it. It is possible that he was not an ordinary person.”

Juqu Mengsun had a cousin called Juqu [Jingsheng] 沮渠[京聲], Marquis of Anyang 安陽侯. He was determined to acquire knowledge and has superficially read through books and records. Because Dharmakṣema came to Hexi to propagate the teaching of the Buddha, the Marquis of Anyang began to read the scriptures and to observe the five prohibitions. The sutras he read, he

could immediately memorize and recite. He always considered that the main task of great men was to devote themselves to studying and acquiring knowledge. When he was younger, he travelled through the Drifting Sands in search of the dharma. When he reached Khotan, at the Great Monastery of Jumodi 瞿摩帝大寺 (Gomatī) he met the Indian dharma master Buddhasena 佛馱斯那 and enquired from him the meaning of the Way. Buddhasena originally studied the Mahāyāna and was a brilliant prodigy who had memorized fifty million gathas. Since he had a clear understanding of meditation techniques, people throughout the Western Regions called him Lion among Men. The Marquis of Anyang received from him the *Chan miyao zhibing jing* 禪祕要治病經. Using the *fan* version, he memorized it thoroughly and shortly after that returned to the east. In Gaochang 高昌, he obtained a copy of the *Guanshiyin jing* 觀世音經 and *Mile erguan* 彌勒二觀, in one *juan* each. Having returned to Hexi, he translated into Chinese and published the *Chanyao* 禪要.

When the illegitimate Wei conquered and annexed the Western Liang, he fled south to the Song. Dimming his ambitions and assuming a humble identity, he had no contacts with the world of men. He usually travelled from one stupa or monastery to the other and ended his life as an upāsaka. When he had first published the *Mile* and *Guanyin* sutras, Meng Yi, Governor of Danyang 丹陽, held these in high regard and generously rewarded him. Afterwards, the nun Huirun 慧濬 from the Zhuyuan monastery 竹園寺 also asked him to translate the *Chan jing*. As the Marquis of Anyang had already been studying it for quite a while, wrote out the translation effortlessly, publishing five *juan* in seventeen days. Not long after, at the Dingling monastery 定林寺 in Zhongshan 鍾山, he also published the *Fofu bannihuan jing* 佛父般泥洹經 in one *juan*.

The Marquis of Anyang lived without a wife or women and had no desire for glory or riches. He spent time with dharma-companions and spread the true teaching. For this reason, monks and laymen all respected and commended him. Afterwards, he unexpectedly became ill and died.

The sutras published by Dharmakṣema only spread to Jianye 建業 during the Yuanjia reign (424-453). Dharma master Huiguan from the Daochang monastery was keen to revive the search for the last part of the *Nirvāṇa sūtra*, and so he requested Emperor Taizu 太祖 of the Song to supply provisions and send śramaṇa Daopu 道普 and ten scribes to go to the west in search of sutras. When they reached Changguang commandery 長廣郡, the boat toppled. Daopu injured his leg, became ill and died. Before dying, he said: “The last part of the *Nirvāṇa sūtra* is not destined by fate to be in Song lands.”

Daopu was a native of Gaochang. He had travelled throughout the Western Regions and visited many kingdoms. He made offerings to the image of the Buddha and carried on his head his begging bowl. The four stupas and the bodhi tree, the Buddha’s footprints and images, all these sites he visited and observed. He was skilled in writing in *fan* script, was fluent in many languages. His travels in foreign lands are recorded separately in a long account. At the time, there also lived in Gaochang a śramaṇa called Fasheng 法盛, who also travelled abroad and left an account in four *juan*. There were also Zhu Fawei 竺法維 and Shi Sengbiao 釋僧表, both of whom journeyed to Buddhist kingdoms.